

Reframing the concept of disinformation in social work: The case of a disadvantaged neighbourhood from the Czech Republic

Kateřina Mikulcová *

Department of Social Work, Faculty of Social Studies, University of Ostrava,
Českobratrská 16, Ostrava 702 00, Czech Republic

*Corresponding author. Department of Social Work, Faculty of Social Studies, University of Ostrava, Českobratrská 16, Ostrava, 702 00, Czech Republic. E-mail: katerina.mikulcova@osu.cz.

Abstract

This article explores how people in disadvantaged neighbourhoods navigate disinformation in everyday life, drawing on concepts from social and affective epistemology. Rather than framing service users as misinformed or irrational, the study highlights how knowledge is constructed through lived experience, emotional trust, and social proximity. The findings show how disinformation is encountered, interpreted, and responded to in everyday life by people living in disadvantaged neighbourhoods. Situated within an anti-oppressive framework, the article argues for recognizing clients as epistemic agents and engaging critically with the socio-material conditions that shape their access to and interpretation of information. Implications for theory, practice, and research are discussed, including the need to understand disinformation as a socially embedded and emotionally mediated phenomenon. The article positions social work as a crucial site for promoting epistemic justice and supporting people living in disadvantaged neighbourhood in navigating increasingly complex information environments.

Keywords: disinformation; disadvantaged neighbourhoods; epistemology; situated knowledge.

© The Author(s) 2025. Published by Oxford University Press on behalf of The British Association of Social Workers.

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Accepted: August 2025

Introduction

Contemporary social work is challenged with the task of delivering reliable and quality information. Yet, with few exceptions (e.g. [Hawkins 2025](#)), there is still very little literature in the field of social work that addresses the issue of disinformation.

Despite this, disinformation remains under-theorized within literature, where it is often treated as a peripheral issue or reduced to a question of misinformation and digital literacy (e.g. [Soprano et al. 2024](#)). This overlooks the fact that disinformation, like all knowledge, circulates through deeply social, relational, and affective processes. Such processes are integral within disadvantaged neighbourhoods.

Contemporary research in media studies and psychology has advanced our understanding of how disinformation spreads (e.g. [Gravino et al. 2024](#)), but such research rarely accounts for the structural inequalities and epistemic injustices that shape how information is received, interpreted, and acted upon. Social work, as a field concerned with empowerment, trust-building, and critical reflection, is uniquely positioned to offer a more situated and relational perspective. Yet, as it stands, there is a notable gap in social work research on how disinformation intersects with experiences of social exclusion, institutional distrust, and emotional coping in everyday life.

This article seeks to address this gap by integrating insights from lay epistemology and affective epistemology into the analysis of how individuals in disadvantaged neighbourhoods navigate conflicting, incomplete, or manipulative information. The main aim of this article is to explore how disinformation is encountered, interpreted, and responded to in everyday life by people living in disadvantaged neighbourhoods.

Disinformation: a new threat that social workers must deal with

Disinformation has become an integral part of everyday life. While public discourse typically associates it with the political domain, it is increasingly recognized as a multidimensional concept that extends into other areas, such as social, cultural, health, and financial domains ([Freiling et al. 2023](#); [Nieminen 2024](#)). Within the academic literature, various terms are used in connection with the topic of (mis/dis)information, each carrying distinct connotations. [Freiling et al. \(2023\)](#) broadly define disinformation as a set of claims that contradict currently available empirical

data. Other sources offer more precise definitions, often distinguishing disinformation from misinformation. The key distinction lies in the intent behind the creation and dissemination of these claims. Misinformation refers to false or misleading information that is not produced or shared with the intention to deceive. It often arises from misunderstanding or lack of knowledge. Disinformation, in contrast, denotes intentionally false information designed to cause harm or deliberately mislead a person, group, or institution (Diepeveen and Pinet 2022; Ahmed et al. 2023). The reception and dissemination of both forms can have serious consequences for individuals and society alike (Nieminen 2024).

Disinformation is not a new phenomenon and has long existed even within traditional media. However, the advent of digital technologies and the proliferation of social media have made disinformation more accessible and easier to circulate. These processes are increasingly difficult to regulate, making individuals more susceptible to disinformation, particularly in relation to shaping their attitudes and opinions on various social and political issues (Butcher 2021; Freiling et al. 2023).

Several factors influence individuals' vulnerability to disinformation. Among the most general are the sheer volume of information and the speed of its circulation, particularly via social media. These dynamics hinder the ability to verify information, distinguish between factual and fabricated content, and identify reliable as opposed to unreliable sources. Consequently, individuals may experience a sense of information overload, which can lead to confusion and uncertainty (Xu et al. 2025). It is thus evident that navigating information in contemporary society is inherently challenging. In addition to the factors already mentioned, scholarly literature also highlights other, more specific vulnerabilities to disinformation—particularly cognitive, demographic, and socio-economic factors (Kirmayer 2024). For this reason, certain social groups are more susceptible to disinformation than others. One of the most vulnerable groups, especially in terms of openness to and lower critical reflection on disinformation, are individuals with experiences of social exclusion (Nieminen 2024).

Reconceptualizing disinformation: association of anti-oppressive social work, situated knowledge, and affective epistemology

Rather than pathologizing individuals as uninformed or irrational in the face of disinformation, the concept of lay epistemology illuminates how people make reasoned, context-sensitive judgments within bounded informational ecologies. This reframing resonates strongly with the commitments of anti-oppressive social work, which seeks to challenge dominant narratives that individualize or moralize marginalization.

As Code's (1991) feminist epistemology insists, knowledge is always shaped by the social location, embodied experience, and epistemic responsibilities of the knower. In anti-oppressive practice, recognizing the situatedness of knowledge means acknowledging that clients' ways of knowing—particularly those from marginalized groups—are not deficient but embedded in histories of exclusion from formal epistemic spaces. Similarly, Haraway's (1988) notion of situated knowledges, partial, embodied, and accountable, challenges the dominance of decontextualized, universalist 'expert' knowledge that often marginalizes or silences lived experience. In the context outlined above, the term 'disinformation' in this article is used not solely in its narrow, intent-based definition (i.e. the knowing and deliberate spread of falsehoods), but also as a socially and epistemically situated phenomenon—as perceived and experienced by people living in disadvantaged neighbourhoods. In line with this theoretical framework, the article, therefore, uses the term in a broader, constructivist sense. This perspective reframes disinformation not as an individual epistemic failure but as a symptom of systemic inequities in access to reliable, culturally resonant, and respectful knowledge infrastructures. People act as lay epistemologists out of necessity, making decisions under conditions of precarity, constrained access, and historical distrust in institutions.

Social work that takes this seriously must move beyond correctional approaches to 'educating' service users, and instead foster epistemic justice—the right to be recognized as a credible knower and to participate in meaning-making processes that shape one's life. Epistemic justice refers to fairness in the distribution of knowledge and in how individuals and groups are recognized and treated as knowers, including whose voices are heard, whose experiences are validated, and whose interpretations of the world are taken seriously (Fricker 2007).

This article also assumes that epistemic practices are inherently affective, a lens that deepens anti-oppressive practice by recognizing how emotional life—often shaped by histories of trauma, exclusion, and resistance—intersects with knowledge-making. The field of affective epistemology explores how emotions such as fear, anxiety, care, and solidarity are not merely psychological responses but epistemic forces that determine what is sought, trusted, or dismissed (Candiotto and Slaby 2022). As Frost-Arnold (2023) notes, emotions can be epistemic drivers, motivating inquiry, or vigilance. In anti-oppressive practice, this helps explain why certain sources are trusted or distrusted—not due to Disinformation *per se*, but due to emotional tuning forged through social and historical experience.

Frost-Arnold (2023) shows that trust is affective and relational, bound to perceptions of respect, recognition, and care. In practice, this means that clients may trust a peer or community worker over other professional not because of a lack of information, but because trust is earned

relationally, not just cognitively. This is particularly important for working with communities that have experienced epistemic injustice—where their knowledge has been systematically dismissed, pathologized, or ignored.

Taken together, these epistemological perspectives enrich anti-oppressive social work by emphasizing that knowledge is social, affective, and political. They shift the analytical and practical focus from correcting false beliefs to interrogating the relational, emotional, and material infrastructures through which knowledge is lived and contested. Social workers are thus called to be not just knowledge brokers, but epistemic allies—amplifying marginalized knowledge, fostering trust, and creating conditions for epistemic dignity (Mikulcová 2025).

Disadvantaged neighbourhoods: a heuristic research context

Disadvantaged neighbourhood could be defined as urban zones where poverty is structurally concentrated (Córdoba Hernandez et al. 2018). Social networks play a crucial role in how disinformation circulates and is interpreted—particularly within disadvantaged neighbourhoods, where patterns of spatial and social exclusion shape access to information. In such settings, networks are often geographically bounded due to residential segregation, leading to limited exposure to diverse perspectives. These neighbourhoods tend to concentrate individuals with similar socio-economic characteristics, most often marked by lower education levels, precarious employment, or reduced institutional trust (Kazmina et al. 2024).

These conditions foster what scholars refer to as ‘socio-economic bubbles’—relational spaces in which people form and maintain ties primarily with others of similar status, background, or beliefs (Bokányi et al. 2021; Gramsch-Calvo and Axhausen 2024). As a result, information flows are shaped by shared experiences and group norms, rather than broad exposure to competing claims or institutional expertise. Trust in information sources is rarely based on objectivity but rather on perceived value alignment—people tend to believe those who reflect their worldview, whether peers, local leaders, or familiar online personalities (Freiling et al. 2023; Xu et al. 2025).

Neighbourhood-based networks thus influence both what information is accessible and how it is interpreted. In more insular communities, limited access to alternative viewpoints or reliable institutional knowledge increases vulnerability to disinformation. As research shows, lower socio-economic status is associated with a higher risk of believing and sharing false or misleading information (Pan et al. 2021). This is not merely a result of ignorance, but of structurally constrained epistemic environments,

where individuals rely on the social relationships available to them to make sense of the world (Madrid-Morales et al. 2021; Mostagir and Siderius 2023).

To better understand how disinformation circulates in disadvantaged neighbourhoods, it is essential to consider the digital divide—a concept that highlights unequal access to digital technologies, internet connectivity, and the skills needed to navigate online information. These disparities directly shape who is exposed to disinformation, how they engage with it, and what resources are available to critically assess it. For some disadvantaged populations, access to the internet—now considered a basic, everyday necessity—is limited or entirely absent (Sanders and Scanlon 2021; Udoudom et al. 2023). As many aspects of daily life—from employment and education to healthcare and civic participation—have moved online, this lack of access deepens existing forms of exclusion (Townsend et al. 2020). The digital divide is shaped by multiple factors, including the inability to afford devices, poor infrastructure in segregated neighbourhoods, and low digital literacy (Ye and Yang 2020). During the COVID-19 pandemic, these inequalities became even more pronounced, but they persist beyond the crisis, continuing to limit opportunities for meaningful social, economic, and political engagement (Aydin 2021; Udoudom et al. 2023). Limited access to ICT also restricts the ability of marginalized communities to build and maintain wider social networks. Interactions often remain confined to in-person or telephone contact, usually within the local area. This constrains not only relationship-building but also access to diverse information sources (Sanders and Scanlon 2021; Gondwe et al. 2025). As a result, the digital divide reinforces informational inequalities, impacting not just communication, but also access to employment, education, and services.

Methodology

The main research question was: How disinformation is encountered, interpreted, and responded to in everyday life by people living in disadvantaged neighbourhoods? The research was carried out using a qualitative research strategy. To obtain data, I used three repeated focus groups with an action group of residents ($n = 7$) living in a specific disadvantaged neighbourhood.

An action group is small, localized, task-focused collective of citizens who work together to address specific issues affecting their community, often with the support of a community worker (see e.g. Ledwith 2011). The given locality was located in a region with one of the highest levels of social exclusion in the Czech Republic and was a former workers' colony. Approximately 650 residents lived in the given locality (~130 of whom were children). A community centre operated in the locality for

10 years, offering a wide range of activities (playroom for children, tutoring, interest groups, discussions, professional lectures, cooking courses). Although exact unemployment and education statistics for this locality are not publicly available, the neighbourhood exhibits characteristics typical of so called '*socially excluded localities*' in the Czech Republic. In such areas, official unemployment rates often reach 80%–85%, with many residents either long-term unemployed or completely detached from the formal labour market. Residents of these localities are also frequently dependent on state welfare benefits and are often subject to debt enforcement proceedings. This economic exclusion is closely linked to low educational attainment: a significant proportion of residents has not completed primary education or possess only basic education, with very few achieving secondary or vocational qualifications ([Agency for Social Inclusion for Czechia 2023](#)).

A cyclical approach to data co-production has been applied, which consisted of the following phases: In the first phase, an interview was conducted with the action group focused on three main questions: (1) how they obtain information; (2) which information they consider trustworthy and how they recognize that the information is trustworthy; (3) whether they encountered any disinformation (described in the description, see the definition in the article) and how they dealt with it (how they verified it, whether they spread it, how they behaved according to it). In the second phase, the data was transcribed and categorized and the individual categories were presented to the action group members for a deeper discussion focused mainly on elaborating on the discovered themes and further discussing them. In the third phase, the overall text was presented to the action group and individual themes were discussed with regard to their validation. This was followed by a discussion on further possible directions for future research.

The participants of the research were seven women, members of the action group of the above-described locality. The women were mothers, aged between twenty-two and seventy years and had experience of living in the locality between nine and thirty years. To preserve the anonymity of the informants, I present information about them only in this aggregate form. The interviews took place in the premises of the community centre, with a round table. The length of one focus group interview was approximately three hours. The interviews were recorded on a dictaphone and transcribed. The main method of analysis of the data collected is thematic analysis (TA) according to [Clarke and Braun \(2019\)](#). Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analysing and interpreting patterns of meaning (themes) in qualitative data. Themes are frequent patterns of meaning in messages that are repeated multiple times by communication partners and subsequently defined and identified.

The research was approved by the Ethics Committee for Research of the Faculty of Social Studies of the University of Ostrava (2025).

Throughout the research I followed Code of Human Research Ethics (BPS 2010).

The effort to achieve the greatest possible validity of the data was made with the knowledge that the data in the research is shaped by the mutual interaction of the researcher and the research participants (Finlay and Gough 2003), therefore, the data itself and the process of obtaining it were cyclically subjected to reflection in all parts of the research (Bradbury-Jones 2007). Control and monitoring of one's own influence on research was carried out by: (1) repeated presence in the research environment; (2) choosing the least intrusive and most natural data collection techniques (interview in a natural environment, anonymous questionnaire); (3) the effort to actively involve people with lived experience in shaping research. It is certainly necessary to reflect the possible limit of desirability within the obtained data. Although this is data obtained from repeated interviews with one group of women from one specific location in a disadvantaged neighbourhood in the Czech Republic, I believe that the data obtained can bring valuable insights into the topic of the epistemology of disinformation.

Data analysis and interpretation

Using a social epistemology lens, the data is categorized into five thematic domains: (1) Epistemic Sources and Trust Formation, (2) Epistemic Tools and Verification Practices, (3) Disinformation Dynamics and Vulnerabilities, (4) Epistemic Authority and Hierarchies, and (5) Resilient Epistemic Strategies. This analysis illustrates how disinformation and knowledge-making are deeply embedded in social relations, emotions, and lived experience. By foregrounding localized epistemic strategies, the study challenges deficit-based models of misinformation and highlights the capacity for everyday epistemic resilience.

Before turning to the detailed analysis, it is worth noting a striking pattern that emerged across the interviews: participants articulated similar ways of evaluating information, navigating doubt, and constructing meaning in response to everyday uncertainties. Although they differed in age, gender, and likely status within the neighbourhood, their knowledge practices consistently drew on relational trust, embodied experience, and local narratives. This uniformity may seem surprising at first, but it reflects a deeper epistemic coherence grounded in shared structural conditions. As relational epistemology reminds us (Fricker 2007; Medina 2013), knowing is not merely a cognitive act but a socially situated practice shaped by power, credibility economies, and histories of recognition or marginalization. In communities marked by long-term exclusion, like the one studied here, affective orientations—such as suspicion, loyalty, or indignation—play a crucial role in shaping epistemic

habits (Frost-Arnold 2023). Rather than viewing this convergence as a limitation, it could be interpreted as a meaningful sign of how epistemic strategies are collectively stabilized through lived experience, structural constraint, and affective investment. These shared orientations may function as adaptive responses to institutional distrust and fragmented information environments.

Epistemic sources and trust formation

Participants repeatedly emphasized that truth emerges from lived, personal experience: **lived experience as epistemic authority**. Statements like *'truth comes from lived experience'* (K1) and *'you have to see it with your own eyes'* (K2) point to a deep-rooted reliance on first-hand knowledge. Trust is predominantly formed through **epistemic proximity**: close friends, family, and known individuals are considered trustworthy sources of information, while institutional sources—such as doctors, news media, or government representatives—are treated with scepticism. For example, in one story, a mother described a misdiagnosis of her child's rash by two different doctors, reinforcing her belief that *'even doctors can lie or be wrong... you think you will learn the truth, but it is not so... but even from a doctor you can learn a lie... the doctor told us that it was impetigo and in the end it was just hives... it was only after a third doctor that we diagnosed it correctly... and in between, how many ointments and medicines were used'*. (K4) And in contrast, another informant stated: *'but if something really scared me, I would mainly ask my family, maybe someone who understands it and knows about it... maybe my brother-in-law knows about it, so I would call him... or maybe call the police, the authorities, the government, the embassy, but that would probably be the last resort'*. (K1) From the above, one can perceive a strong **distrust in institutional knowledge** associated with repeated emphasis on institutional fallibility, especially from marginalized positioning. Online communities like XX (Czech online Facebook community for parents with children) and localized Facebook groups are used as trusted environments where personal stories are shared, read, and validated. These are not merely information sources but also **social spaces where knowledge is co-constructed** and reinforced through repetition and resonance.

Epistemic tools and verification practices

The data reveal complex and pragmatic approaches to verifying information. Participants engage in what may be termed **lay triangulation**—cross-checking facts across multiple Facebook groups, observing repeated patterns in discussions, and turning to people they consider experienced.

‘When I see that some experiences are repeated there... or that someone is very active in that group, who gets a lot of likes...’ (K5) Digital tools like ChatGPT are used as **epistemic assistants**. Users describe the artificial intelligence (AI) as a helpful but imperfect guide, emphasizing the importance of asking the same question multiple times to test consistency. ChatGPT is used to understand medical diagnoses, prepare contracts, help children with homework, and even suggest recipes. This reflects a shift in how epistemic authority is distributed, with AI becoming a semi-trusted actor, especially in contexts where institutional support is lacking or difficult to access. *‘I’m trying to ask questions differently, it helps me a lot... at school the children have different homework, it’s been a long time since I was at school... my son came to me with geometry... so I put it in the chat GPT and I got the result...’* (K1) *‘I let chat GPT explain me the medical reports... sometimes the doctor doesn’t always explain it, even if you ask...’* (K7) The visual and **embodied nature of evidence** is crucial: several participants stated that they only believe something when they *‘see it with their own eyes... not just written somewhere or some picture on Facebook’*. (K2) Participants also assess the credibility of Facebook posts based on the profiles of commenters (e.g. number of friends), the perceived neutrality of the group or page, and the multiplication of similar comments across different posts. **In essence, verification practices are deeply social and emotionally calibrated.**

Disinformation dynamics and vulnerabilities

Participants face an overwhelming volume of information and express feelings of exhaustion and confusion about what is trustworthy. The participants’ stories were filled with **feelings of overload and affective fatigue**. *‘there was an accident... and you know what car it was and the colour, maybe you know the person... and it’s different in the newspapers, I knew the truth... and they lie in the newspapers... and then everyone believes it... they trample on the person who was innocent in the discussions... I don’t trust television’*. (K1) During crises like the COVID-19 pandemic or the war in Ukraine, fear and uncertainty intensify **epistemic vulnerability**. One woman remarked that *‘when you’re closed at home... or alone, you start to believe everything’*.

Numerous **examples of disinformation** were shared: *‘that covid masks contain worms’*, *‘that bleach can cure cancer’*, or *‘that police would fine smokers without masks in Covid-19 period’*. There was also frequent misinformation that a private owner was going to sell apartments in a given area and people would have to move out. There was also misinformation about child abductions. Participants often took actions in response to such claims—cutting open masks to check for worms. *‘We tried cutting*

the masks at home, there were videos on the internet where people were cutting them... even after cutting them, they believed that the worms were there... A lot of people stopped wearing masks or at least changed their old masks for new ones... (K7) Historical memories of disinformation, especially from the 1990s, were recalled to highlight how disinformation is not new, but **deeply embedded in neighbourhood experience**. Participants described events like the rumoured arrival of skinheads, which mobilized entire neighbourhoods in fear, despite no violence ultimately occurring. Some of the events described generated fear and urgency and thus served as **epistemic accelerators**. Rumours during crises (e.g. Covid, war, expected skin attack) create an atmosphere where people *'believe everything'* out of fear or protective instincts. *'Sometimes it happened that the news would spread through the streets that... there will be a raid and the skinheads will come, there were a lot of Roma living in the street... they chased the children home, all the big boys and men, looking for weapons, sticks, bats... the skinheads never came... it was such an echo, it carried across the whole street... everyone was afraid... only the men who could somehow defend themselves were left outside... but nothing ever happened...'* (K6)

Epistemic authority and hierarchies

Authority in this context is **fluid** and often contested. On one hand, individuals refer to doctors or officials due to their titles and perceived expertise—some even said they would do whatever a doctor told them. On the other hand, these same figures are often distrusted, especially when their claims contradict lived experience. The above depended a lot on how the specific informant assessed their lived experience with the given knowledge, e.g. *'When I had my first child and didn't have that much experience, I would have trusted the doctor... probably not something completely stupid like giving the child a pacifier or something, but if he told me to feed the child with this or give him this, I would have done it... not now, now I have the experience and I can handle it myself...'* (K1)

Generational and digital divides further complicate the landscape. Older individuals tend to trust print media and television, while younger generations are more comfortable seeking verification online. Participants described frustration in trying to *'talk someone out of'* false beliefs if that person lacks digital literacy or access. One of the informants spoke about her aunt: *'What was written is true and it's impossible to explain it to her... for example, the war, she believes that soldiers will arrive in a moment... she has daughters who go online, but when it's in the news, it's just a given... it's a generational thing, older people find it harder to talk things out... she even believes advertising... even though*

she knows that I've never lied to her, it's hard to believe me'. (K5) As for the **digital divide**, the informants agreed that in the area where they lived, people who lived there did not have the Internet or computers or mobile phones to be able to search for something on the Internet. *'It's difficult for these socially weaker people, they have no way to verify it, they simply believe what someone tells them*'. (K4)

Community leaders play a critical role in local knowledge circulation. These individuals are seen as **local epistemic hubs** of reliable information, and residents often refer to them when they encounter uncertainty. One participant described herself as a *'living ChatGPT'* (K2) frequently called upon to help others navigate bureaucratic, medical, or educational issues.

Resilient epistemic strategies

Rather than being passive consumers of disinformation, participants actively seek to make sense of their world using all tools available—technological, interpersonal, and experiential. These practices reflect a form of community-based epistemic agency, where knowledge is produced and validated collaboratively, even under conditions of marginalization and systemic distrust. Despite the vulnerabilities and disinformation, participants exhibit numerous strategies of epistemic resilience. The most frequently cited example was the Covid-19 era. During the pandemic, local networks mobilized to sew thousands of masks when medical supplies were scarce. Knowledge-sharing and mutual aid became crucial practices. *'So, for us, sewing masks was an example. At a time when there was a shortage of masks everywhere... or they were terribly expensive, we thought it was still a good idea to wear them, that we wouldn't be breathing in each other's faces... there was a seamstress living in our area and so we went to see her... we had a very simple sewing machine and she taught us how to sew... we sewed several thousand masks... then it became a big deal, we even sewed them for hospitals... we sewed 18 hours a day*'. (K1)

Discussion

The findings of this study have important implications for the future of social work theory, practice, and research, particularly in relation to epistemic practices and disinformation in disadvantaged neighbourhoods. In a context where trust in institutions is declining and digital information ecologies are becoming increasingly complex (Freiling et al. 2023; Xu et al. 2025), the relevance of social work as an epistemic and relational practice becomes ever more critical.

First, these findings invite a reconsideration of how knowledge is conceptualized and communicated in social work. Traditional models have often prioritized the transmission of accurate, evidence-based content from professionals to clients. While this remains essential, the data from this study highlight that people in disadvantaged neighbourhoods also rely on alternative epistemic resources—such as lived experience, interpersonal trust, and emotional resonance—when evaluating information and making decisions. Rather than positioning these modes of knowing in opposition, we suggest they reflect different but equally valid forms of knowledge generation. This aligns with insights from social and affective epistemology, which emphasize that knowledge is not only cognitive and factual, but also situated, relational, and shaped by affective dynamics (Code 1991; Frost-Arnold 2023). For social work theory, this underscores the importance of recognizing clients as epistemic agents with their own legitimate ways of knowing, and encourages a more dialogical, reflexive practice that values both evidence and experience.

Second, the findings underscore the need for epistemic humility and reflexivity in social work practice. Social workers frequently operate within institutional frameworks that assume a clear distinction between credible knowledge and misinformation. However, in practice, the boundary between these categories is often blurred by histories of mistrust, experiences of exclusion, and differing modes of sense-making. Social workers must, therefore, recognize and engage with the informal and emotionally attuned knowledge systems that clients rely upon. This includes working collaboratively with neighbourhood knowledge holders—such as local leaders, online peer groups, and extended kin networks—who serve as epistemic anchors in the absence of institutional trust (Mikulcová 2025). These insights align closely with the principles of anti-oppressive social work (e.g. Dominelli 2002), which emphasize the importance of challenging dominant knowledge systems, validating lived experience, and fostering empowerment. Anti-oppressive practice demands that social workers critically examine whose knowledge is legitimized and whose is marginalized. The recognition of clients' epistemic agency, especially in contexts of disinformation, aligns with broader commitments to resisting epistemic injustice (Fricker 2007) and promoting inclusive knowledge practices.

Furthermore, the findings draw attention to the role of digital exclusion and the digital divide as not merely technological issues but as dimensions of epistemic and social injustice. Limited access to devices, digital literacy, and stable internet connections constrains people's ability to verify information, engage with services, and participate fully in public life. Social work practice must adapt to these conditions by actively addressing digital inequalities (Aydin 2021; Sanders and Scanlon 2021). Digital inclusion efforts should go beyond access to encompass critical

digital literacy and navigation of complex online information environments (van Deursen and Helsper 2015).

From a research perspective, this study points to the value of ethnographic, participatory, and qualitative methodologies for understanding how disinformation is lived, negotiated, and sometimes resisted in everyday contexts. Rather than focusing solely on content analysis or the accuracy of beliefs, future social work research should prioritize understanding the relational, emotional, and contextual processes through which knowledge is made. This entails a shift from framing individuals as ‘misinformed’ to recognizing their strategies of epistemic resilience—such as triangulating sources, relying on trusted networks, or withholding belief until personally validated (similarly sees Medina 2013).

These findings also raise broader questions about the political role of social work in communities where disinformation circulates and trust in public institutions is often weak. Disadvantaged neighbourhoods, like those explored in this study, are frequently targeted by populist and exclusionary ideologies that exploit feelings of neglect, fear, or frustration (Garrett 2019; Lorenz 2022). In such contexts, social workers are not just service providers; they are also public actors who can play a key role in supporting democracy and social cohesion. Social work has long been recognized as a profession that operates at the intersection of individual lives and structural inequalities (Dominelli 2002). When people are made to feel that their knowledge and experiences are dismissed or devalued—exactly what philosopher Miranda Fricker (2007) calls ‘epistemic injustice’—it becomes even more important for social workers to listen carefully, validate local perspectives, and create spaces for dialogue. This means recognizing that some of the stories people tell—even when they are based on disinformation—often express real concerns about inequality, abandonment, or exclusion.

By facilitating spaces where people can reflect together, share experiences, and ask critical questions, social workers can help strengthen what scholars call epistemic resilience—a community’s ability to make sense of the world in ways that are not easily captured by top-down narratives (similarly see Medina 2013). This role is especially urgent today, as many European societies are grappling with rising authoritarianism and political polarisation. In this light, social work becomes not only about helping individuals, but also about defending democratic values, promoting critical thinking, and supporting the collective capacity to challenge harmful ideologies. As Abramovitz and Zelnick (2015) argue, the everyday practice of social work can—and should—be a site of resistance to the forces that seek to silence or marginalize communities.

Finally, these findings invite a broader reflection on the role of social work as an epistemic practice. In an era of contested truths, emotional polarization, and growing inequality, social workers are not only service providers but also mediators of trust, interpreters of complex

information, and facilitators of epistemic justice. The profession must embrace this role by developing theoretical, practical, and pedagogical tools that acknowledge the complexity of knowledge and the importance of relational trust (Gray and Webb 2013; Fook 2016).

In sum, this study contributes to a reimagining of social work's epistemic responsibilities in the digital and disinformation age. It affirms the importance of grounding practice in the lived realities of clients, engaging critically with how knowledge circulates, and supporting communities in navigating their epistemic landscapes with agency and care.

While this article has focused on the situated epistemic practices of residents in disadvantaged neighbourhoods, these practices do not exist in a vacuum. They are shaped by broader discursive conditions—media representations, policy narratives, institutional language—that influence how residents interpret their realities and how their knowledge is received or dismissed by professionals and institutions. These discourses not only mediate the relationship between residents and social workers, but also reflect deeper political currents, including growing scepticism among socially and economically marginalized groups toward dominant institutions and democratic processes. Exploring these discursive conditions over a longer time frame would offer valuable insights into how mistrust, recognition, and resistance evolve, and how they intersect with shifting political dynamics. This article sees this as a crucial avenue for future research aimed at understanding the role of social work in supporting democratic resilience and epistemic justice in a time of polarization and inequality.

Conflict of interest

There are no financial interests or benefits that have arisen from the direct applications of our research.

Funding

This work has been produced with the financial support of the European Union under the: Biography of Fake News with a Touch of AI: Dangerous Phenomenon through the Prism of Modern Human Sciences project no.: CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008724 via the Operational Programme Jan Ámos Komenský.

References

- Abramovitz, M., and Zelnick, J. (2015) 'Privatization in the Human Services: Implications for Direct Practice', *Clinical Social Work Journal*, 43: 283–93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10615-015-0546-1>

- Agency for Social Inclusion for Czechia. (2023) *Social Exclusion Index*. https://www.socialni-zaclenovani.cz/index_socialniho_vyloucenio-indexu/, accessed 6 Apr. 2025.
- Ahmed, S., Madrid-Morales, D., and Tully, M. (2023) 'Social Media, Misinformation, and Age Inequality in Online Political Engagement', *Journal of Information Technology & Politics*, 20: 269–85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19331681.2022.2096743>.
- Aydin, M. (2021) 'Does the Digital Divide Matter? Factors and Conditions that Promote ICT Literacy', *Telematics and Informatics*, 58: 101536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2020.101536>
- Bokányi, E., et al. (2021) 'Universal Patterns of Long-Distance Commuting and Social Assortativity in Cities', *Scientific Reports*, 11: 20829. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-00416-1>.
- BPS. (2010) Av BPS Code of Human Research Ethics. <https://cms.bps.org.uk/sites/default/files/2022-06/BPS%20Code%20of%20Human%20Research%20Ethics%20281%29.pdf>, accessed 6 Apr. 2025.
- Bradbury-Jones, C. (2007) 'Enhancing Rigor in Qualitative Health Research: Exploring Subjectivity Through Peshkin's I's', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 59: 290–8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04306.x>
- Butcher, P. (2021) 'COVID-19 as a Turning Point in the Fight Against Disinformation', *Nature Electronics*, 4: 7–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-020-00532-2>.
- Candiotta, L., and Slaby, J. (2022) 'Introduction: The Role of Emotions in Epistemic Practices and Communities', *Topoi*, 41: 835–7. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11245-022-09839-5>
- Clarke, V., and Braun, V. (2019) 'Reflecting on Reflexive Thematic Analysis', *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, 11: 589–97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2159676X.2019.1628806>
- Code, L. (1991) *What Can She Know?*, *Feminist Theory and the Construction of Knowledge*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Córdoba Hernandez, R., González García, I., and Guerrero Periñán, G. (2018) Urban Poverty Partnership: Report About Urban Deprivation/Poverty Observatories in the European Union. https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/system/files/ged/report_about_urban_deprivation_and_poverty_-_observatories_in_the_europe.pdf, accessed 7 May 2025.
- Diepeveen, S., and Pinet, M. (2022) 'User Perspectives on Digital Literacy as a Response to Misinformation', *Development Policy Review*, 40. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dpr.12671>.
- Dominelli, L. (2002) *Anti-Oppressive Social Work Theory and Practice*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan. ISBN-13. 978–0333771556
- Finlay, L., and Gough, B. (2003) *Reflexivity: A Practical Guide for Researchers in Health and Social Sciences*. Malden, MA: Blackwell Science
- Fook, J. (2016) *Social Work: A Critical Approach to Practice*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd. ISBN 13: 9781473913028.
- Freiling, I., et al. (2023) 'Believing and Sharing Misinformation, Fact-Checks, and Accurate Information on Social Media: The Role of Anxiety During COVID-19', *New Media & Society*, 25: 141–62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448211011451>.
- Fricke, M. (2007) *Epistemic Injustice: Power and the Ethics of Knowing*, online edn., Oxford: Oxford Academic. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198237907.001.0001>
- Frost-Arnold, K. (2023) *Who Should We Be Online?: A Social Epistemology for the Internet*. New York, US: OUP USA.

- Garrett, P. M. (2019) *Welfare Words: Critical Social Work and Social Policy*. London: Sage.
- Gramsch-Calvo, B., and Axhausen, K. W. (2024) 'The Importance of the Social Environment on Leisure Destination Choice: A Mixed Multinomial Analysis of Homophilic Preferences', *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 52: 1650–68. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23998083241303198>.
- Gondwe, G., et al. (2025) 'Misinformation and Digital Inequalities: Comparing How Different Demographic Groups Get Exposed to and Engage with False Information', *Mass Communication and Society*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15205436.2025.2474139>.
- Gravino, P., Prevedello, G., and Brugnoli, E. (2024) 'Online News Ecosystem Dynamics: Supply, Demand, Diffusion, and the Role of Disinformation', *Applied Network Science*, 9: 40.
- Haraway, D. (1988) 'Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective', *Feminist Studies*, 14: 575–99.
- Hawkins, R. L. (2025) 'When the Lie Becomes the Truth: Misinformation and Conspiracy Theories in Social Work', *Social Work Research*, 49: 3–7. <https://doi.org/10.1093/swr/sva003>
- Kazmina, Y., et al. (2024) 'Socio-Economic Segregation in a Population-scale', *Social Networks*, 78: 279–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2024.02.005>.
- Kirmayer, L. J. (2024) 'Science and Sanity: A Social Epistemology of Misinformation, Disinformation, and the Limits of Knowledge', *Transcultural Psychiatry*, 61: 795–808. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13634615241296301>
- Ledwith, M. (2011) *Community Development: A Critical Approach*. Bristol: Policy Press. ISBN 978–1847426468.
- Lorenz, W. (2022) 'Social Work Epistemology in Political Contexts–Historical Reflections and Future Perspectives', *Fórum Sociální Práce*, 2: 9–20.
- Nieminen, H. (2024) 'Why Does Disinformation Spread in Liberal Democracies? The Relationship between Disinformation, Inequality, and the Media', *Javnost - The Public*, 31: 123–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13183222.2024.2311019>.
- Medina, J. (2013) *The Epistemology of Resistance: Gender and Racial Oppression, Epistemic Injustice, and The Social Imagination*. New York: Oxford University Press. ISBN: 9780199929047.
- Mikulcová, K. (2025) Reimagining Social Work with Disinformation in Disadvantaged Neighborhoods as Feminist Epistemic Practice. *Affilia*. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/08861099251362815>
- Mostagir, M., and Siderius, J. (2023) 'Social Inequality and the Spread of Misinformation', *Management Science*, 69: 968–95. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2022.4380>
- Madrid-Morales, D. et al. (2021) 'Motivations for Sharing Misinformation: A Comparative Study in Six Sub-Saharan African Countries', *International Journal of Communication*, 15: 1200–19.
- Pan, W., Liu, D., and Fang, J. (2021) 'An Examination of Factors Contributing to the Acceptance of Online Health Misinformation', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12: 630268. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.630268>
- Sanders, C. K., and Scanlon, E. (2021) 'The Digital Divide Is a Human Rights Issue: Advancing Social Inclusion Through Social Work Advocacy', *Journal of Human Rights and Social Work*, 6: 130–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41134-020-00147-9>.

- Soprano, M. et al. (2024) 'Cognitive Biases in Fact-Checking and Their Countermeasures: A Review', *Information Processing & Management*, 61: 103672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2024.103672>
- Townsend, L., Salemink, K., and Wallace, C. D. (2020) 'Gypsy-Traveller Communities in the United Kingdom and the Netherlands: Socially and Digitally Excluded?', *Media, Culture & Society*, 42: 637–53. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443718807381>.
- Udoudom, U., et al. (2023) 'Media Literacy and Its Implications for The Understanding of Truth and Reality: A Philosophical Exploration', *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 4: 4244–57. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.04.12.08>.
- van Deursen, A. J. A. M., and Helsper, E. J. (2015) 'The Third-Level Digital Divide: Who Benefits Most from Being Online?', in L. Robinson, S. R. Cotten, and J. Schulz (eds.) *Communication and Information Technologies Annual (Studies in Media and Communications, Vol. 10*, pp. 29–52. Leeds: Emerald Group Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2050-206020150000010002>
- Xu, Y., et al. (2025) 'Opinion Convergence and Management: Opinion Dynamics in Interactive Group Decision-Making', *European Journal of Operational Research*, 323: 938–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2024.12.046>
- Ye, L., and Yang, H. (2020) 'From Digital Divide to Social Inclusion: A Tale of Mobile Platform Empowerment in Rural Areas', *Sustainability*, 12: 2424. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12062424>.

© The Author(s) 2025. Published by Oxford University Press on behalf of The British Association of Social Workers.

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

British Journal of Social Work, 2025, 00, 1–18

<https://doi.org/10.1093/bjsw/bcaf180>

Original article